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OPTIMIZATION OF STRESS CONDITIONS OF FORCED DEGRADATION STUDY BY UV SPECTROPHOTOMETER

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ABSTRACT

Forced degradation study (FDS) is an emerging trend, requisite to be performed and reported while filing abbreviated new drug application (ANDA) and investigational new drug application (IND) application. Modern analytical instruments like HPLC, UPLC, and LC-MS etc. are commonly used throughout the intact study. These methods are more specific, accurate but also costly and time consuming. Optimization of stress conditions is a critical part of study as standard values are not revealed by regulatory authorities. The objective of this work is to explore role of UV spectrophotometer in FDS and to overcome above problems. In this study, FDS of Gallic acid has been carried out using UV spectrophotometer. Gallic acid was exposed to different stress conditions like acidic and alkaline hydrolysis, oxidation, dry heat and photolytic degradation. UV spectrum of sample subjected to stress conditions was recorded and compared with standard spectrum. It was found that Gallic acid has undergone degradation in acidic (HCl), alkaline (NaOH) and oxidative media (H₂O₂). However, it was found stable at thermal and photolytic stress conditions. The present study explains usefulness of UV-Visible spectrophotometer in FDS which helps to save time and expenditure required for study.

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INTRODUCTION

All pharmaceutical substances inevitably contain impurities and the role of ethical pharmaceutical industry is to define an impurity profile that is acceptable for the intended use of a given drug, without compromising its therapeutic safety and efficacy. The stability of a drug product or a drug substance is a critical parameter in which may affect purity, potency and safety. Changes in drug stability can risk patient safety by formation of a toxic degradation product(s) or deliver a lower dose than expected. Therefore it is essential to know the purity profile and behavior of a drug substance under various environmental conditions which could be possible by forced degradation study [1,2].

Forced degradation study is an emerging trend, requisite to be performed and reported while filing INDA and NDA application. FDS is defined as the stability testing of drug substances and drug products undertaken to elucidate intrinsic stability attributes. Stress testing is performed by exposing drug substances and drug products to extreme conditions, such as pH, photolysis, oxidation and temperature, over a very short time period. It also referred to as forced degradation studies [3, 4]. Pharmaceutical companies perform forced-degradation studies during preformulation to help select compounds and excipients for further development, to facilitate salt selection or formulation optimization, and to produce samples for developing stability-indicating analytical methods. Stress testing provides information about degradation mechanisms and potential degradation products. This information then can be used to develop manufacturing processes or to select proper packaging. It may also help in preparing reference material of identified degradation products. Although preformulation work is part of early-phase drug development, stress testing often is repeated when manufacturing processes, product composition, and analytical procedures are refined and reach a more final state [5].

Objective of Forced Degradation Studies:

The forced degradation study is carried out for the following objective

- To develop and validate a stability indicating method
- To determine degradation pathways of drug substances and drug products (e.g., during development phase)
- To identify impurities related to drug substances or excipients
- To understand the drug molecule chemistry
- To generate more stable formulations
- To generate a degradation profile that mimics what would be observed in a formal stability study under ICH conditions
- To solve stability-related problems (e.g., mass balance)

Selection of Stress Conditions

In designing forced degradation studies, it must be remembered that more strenuous conditions than those used for accelerated studies (25°C/60% RH or 40°C/75% RH) should be used. A minimal list of stress factors suggested for forced degradation studies must include acid and base hydrolysis, thermal degradation, photolysis, and oxidation and may include freeze-thaw cycles and shear. However, some scientists have found it practical to begin at extreme conditions (80°C or even higher, 0.5N NaOH, 0.5N HCl, 3% H₂O₂) and testing at shorter (2, 5, 8, and 24 hrs, etc) multiple time points, thus allowing for a rough evaluation of rates of degradation. Testing at early time points may permit distinction between primary degradant and their secondary degradation products. This strategy allows for better degradation pathway determination. It must be noted that a forced degradation study is a “living process” and should be done along the developmental time line as long as changes in the stability-indicating methods, manufacturing processes, or formulation changes are ongoing. Forced degradation is only considered complete after the manufacturing process is finalized, formulations established, and test procedures developed and qualified. The following conditions by no means exhaustive and should be adjusted by the researcher as needed to generate ~10% degradation of the API. The nature of the particular drug substance will determine in which direction to adjust the stress conditions [6].

Acid and base hydrolysis:

The hydrolytic degradation of a new drug in acidic and alkaline conditions can be studied by refluxing the drug in 0.1 N HCl/NaOH for 8 h. If reasonable degradation is seen, testing can be stopped at this point. However, in case no degradation is seen under these conditions, the drug should be refluxed in acid/alkali of higher strengths and for longer duration. Alternatively, if total degradation is seen after subjecting the drug to initial conditions, acid/alkali strength can be decreased along with decrease in the reaction temperature. In a similar manner, degradation under neutral conditions can be started by refluxing the drug in water for 12 h. Reflux time should be increased if no degradation is seen. If the drug is found to degrade completely, both time and temperature of study can be decreased [8, 9].

Oxidative degradation:

Forced degradation studies designed to test the susceptibility of compounds to oxidative degradation. To test for oxidation, it is suggested to use hydrogen peroxide in the concentration range of 3–30%. In some drugs extensive degradation is seen when exposed to 3% of hydrogen peroxide for very shorter time period at room temperature. In other cases exposure to high concentration of hydrogen peroxide, even under extreme condition does not cause any significant degradation. The behavior is on expected lines, as some drugs are in fact oxidisable, while there are others that are not. The latter are not expected to show any change even in the presence of high dose of oxidizing agent.

Photolytic Degradation:

The photolytic studies should be carried out by exposure to light, using either a combination of cool white and ultraviolet fluorescent lamps, or one among the xenon and metal halide lamps. Exposure energy should be minimum of 1.2 million lux h fluorescent light and 200W h/m² UV and if decomposition is not seen, the intensity should be increased by five times. In case still no decomposition takes place, the drug can be declared photostable [8, 9].

Thermal Degradation:

Thermal-humidity stress testing: forced degradation studies designed to test the stability of compounds by exposing them to different thermal and humidity conditions. Most companies perform thermal-humidity stress testing studies in both open and closed containers. Most companies typically test at a range of 51–70 °C. If the drug substance does not degrade easily, some of companies stress solid-state samples at ≥ 90 °C, and few companies stress samples at 71–90 °C [8, 9].

A minimum of four samples should be generated for every stress condition, viz. the blank solution stored under normal conditions, the blank subjected to stress in the same manner as the drug solution, zero time sample containing the drug which is stored under normal conditions and the drug solution subjected to stress treatment. The comparison of the results of these provides real assessment of the changes. Furthermore, it is advised to withdraw samples at different time periods for each reaction condition. By doing so, one can get a clear idea on the number of products formed, their relative strengths and whether they are stable or unstable, resulting further in newer products. This information is essential in establishment of SIAMs[8, 9].

Finalization of stress condition is an integral part of forced degradation study in which strength of acid, alkali, oxidizing agent, temperature, light intensity to which API or dosage forms has to be exposed are finalized. It is observed that sophisticated chromatographic techniques like HPLC, HPTLC or UPLC are being used to finalize stress conditions. It can be possible by UV-Visible spectrophotometer. In current work, it has been tried to explore role of UV- Visible spectrophotometer in forced degradation study. Gallic acid, therapeutically significant phytochemical, was selected for the study [8, 9].

Gallic acid

Gallic acid (3, 4, 5-Trihydroxybenzoic acid) has molecular formula C₇H₆O₅ and molecular weight 170. Gallic acid has anti-fungal and anti-viral properties. It acts as an antioxidant and helps to protect human cells against oxidative damage. Gallic acid was found to show cytotoxicity against cancer cells, without harming healthy cells. Gallic acid is used as a remote astringent in cases of internal hemorrhage. Gallic acid is also used to treat albuminuria and diabetes. Some ointments to treat psoriasis and external hemorrhoids contain Gallic acid.

Experimental**Instrument and material****Instrument**

Schimadzu 1600 double beam UV/Visible Spectrophotometer
Single pan analytical balance Dhona 200 D
Hot air oven

Apparatus

Volumetric flask (10 ml, 50 ml), Beaker, Pipette, Funnel,
Water bath, Burner, Thermometer, Whatmann filter paper #41

Chemicals

All chemicals and reagents used were of analytical grade (HCL, NaOH, H₂O₂ and Methanol)

Method**Preparation of standard solution:**

Standard stock solution was prepared by dissolving and diluting 10 mg of Gallic acid to 10ml in distilled water to obtain concentration of 1 mg/ml. It was sonicated for few minutes and finally filtered by Whatmann filter paper #41. 100 μ l portion of the stock solution was further diluted to 10 ml with distilled water. The resulting solution was scanned in the range of 200 - 400 against blank [10].

Figure 1: UV spectrum of pure Gallic acid.

Preparation of calibration curve:

Aliquots of 20-120 μl portions of stock solutions were transferred to a series of 10-ml volumetric flasks and volume were made up to mark with distilled water. Solutions were scanned in the range of 200-400 nm against blank. The absorption maxima were found to be at 220 nm against blank. The calibration curve was plotted to assure linearity and reproducibility [10].

Table I Observation table of beers law study.

Sr. No.	Concentration of GA $\mu\text{g/ml}$	Absorbance at 220 nm
1.	0.000	0.000
2.	4.000	0.274
3.	8.000	0.515
4.	10.000	0.652
5.	16.000	1.013
6.	20.000	1.228

Figure 2 Calibration curve of Gallic acid.

Forced degradation study:

Stability studies were performed by forced degradation study of Gallic acid and it includes the study of effect of temperature, oxidation, acid degradation and base degradation as per ICH guidelines. Stress conditions studied are as mentioned in the Table II.

Table II Stress Conditions.

Sr.No	Type of Degradation	Strength	Temperature in °C	Time in Hours
1	Acid	0.1N ,1N & 5N HCL	27	4
2	Alkali	0.1N,1N& 5N NaOH	27	4
3	Oxidation	3% & 30 % H ₂ O ₂	27	4
4	Thermal stress	NA	60	2,4 and 6
5	Photo	NA	Environmental temperature	2,4 and 6

Acid Degradation

Accurately weighed 10 mg bulk drug was taken in 10 ml volumetric flask One ml of methanol was added to dissolve the drug and then made up the volume by 0.1 N HCl. Then, this solution was kept for refluxing for 6 hours at 70 °C in water bath. 100 µl portions from the above solution were withdrawn and further diluted to 10 ml with distilled water 4 hours. The resulting solution was neutralized and the scanned in the range of 200 - 400 nm against blank prepared by the same way. Procedure was repeated with 1 N and 5 N HCl. Spectra are shown in figure 3 [11-13].

Alkali Degradation

Accurately weighed 10 mg bulk drug was taken in 10 ml volumetric flask One ml of methanol was added to dissolve the drug and then made up the volume by 0.1 N NaOH. Thereafter solution was kept for refluxing for 6 hours at 70 °C in water bath. 100 µl portions from the above solution were withdrawn and further diluted to 10 ml with distilled water in at 0, 2, 4, and 6 hours. The resulting solution was neutralized and scanned in the range of 200 - 400 nm against blank prepared by the same way. Procedure was repeated with 1 N and 5 N NaOH. Spectra are shown in figure 4[11-13].

Oxidative Degradation

Accurately weighed 10 mg bulk drug was taken in two 10 ml volumetric flask. One ml of methanol was added in each to dissolve the drug. Then 0.3 % v/v and 3%v/v H₂O₂ was added separately to make volume up to the mark. Thereafter solutions were kept for refluxing for 6 hours at 70 °C in water bath. 100 µl portions from each solution were withdrawn and further diluted to 10 ml with distilled water in at 4 hours. The resulting solution was scanned in the range of 200 - 400 nm against blank prepared by the same way. Spectra are shown in figure 5 [11-13].

Dry Heat Degradation

For dry heat degradation, Gallic acid was placed in oven at 60°C for 2, 4 and 6 hours under dry heat condition in the dark and then cooled to room temperature. Degradation samples were subjected to UV analysis after suitable dilutions with water. Blank was generated by the same manner. UV spectra of degradation sample compared with that of standard. Spectra are shown in figure 6[11-13].

Photo degradation:

A specific amount of bulk drug was taken in a cleaned Petridish and the exposed to sunlight for 8 hours. From that in each 2 hours interval accurately 10mg of bulk drug was weighed and was transferred to 10 ml volumetric flask and the volume was adjusted with water, which gives a concentration of 1000µg/ml. Aliquots about 0.1 ml were withdrawn and diluted to 10 ml with water. Diluted solutions were scanned under 200-400 nm to record UV spectrum and compared with UV spectrum of pure Gallic acid. Spectra are shown in figure 7 [4,11-13].

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

In the study, it was found that UV spectrum of acid, alkali and oxidative degradation sample did not match with UV spectrum of pure Gallic acid. Therefore, it could be concluded that Gallic acid underwent acid, alkali and oxidative degradation. However, UV spectrum of thermal photolytic degradation sample found identical to standard spectrum indicating thermal and photo stability of Gallic acid at 60 °C up to 6 hrs. The spectrum of individual sample at various stress conditions are shown in following figures.

A.

B.

C.

Figure 3 Acid degradation sample spectrum of 0.1N, 1N & 5N HCL at 4 hr as A, B and C respectively.

A.

B.

C.

Figure 4 Alkali degradation sample spectrum of 0.1N, 1N & 5N NaOH at 4 hr as A, B and C respectively.

A.

B.

Figure 5 0.3 % v/v and 3%v/v H₂O₂ degraded samples spectrum at 2 hr as A and B respectively.

Figure 6 Thermal degradation sample spectrum at 2, 4 and 6 hr as A, B and C respectively.

Figure 7 UV Spectrum of Gallic acid in sunlight after 2hr (A) and after 4 hr(B).

Table III Summary of forced degradation study.

Sr.No	Type of Degradation	Strength	Degradation
1	Acid	0.1N, 1N & 5N HCL 27 °C, 4 hrs	+++
2	Alkali	0.1N, 1N & 5N NaOH 27 °C, 4 hrs	+++
3	Oxidation	3% & 30 % H ₂ O ₂ 27 °C, 4 hrs	+++
4	Thermal stress	60 °C, 2, 4 & 6 hrs	---
5	Photo	2, 4 & 6 hrs	---

+++ Degradation is occurred at all conditions.

--- No degradation is occurred at all conditions.

CONCLUSION

With regard to the above discussion, it is concluded that stress parameters of forced degradation study can be optimized satisfactorily by means of spectrophotometer at the initial stage and remaining part of the study can be completed by means of sophisticated and hyphenated techniques. So spectrophotometer may help to reduce analysts' dependency on sophisticated and hyphenated techniques for the entire work as it partly done by it. UV- spectrophotometer can evidently be incorporated to set stress condition which makes study more effective in the interest of cost and time which are of a great concern today.

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